

Proteoforms and their expanding role in biomedical research

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**Proteo
Vilamoura**

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Rationale behind looking at intact proteins

Many protein forms (proteoforms) from a single gene

What is a proteoform?

Canonical
Sequence
(UniProtKB)

Endogenous proteolysis
mRNA splicing
Mutations
SNPs

Site specific features:
Govern activity, localization, interactions, half-life

A distinct molecular form of a protein product arising from a single gene

The Consortium for Top-Down Proteomics

Proteoforms in biomedical & clinical research

- Proteoform-level knowledge is essential to understand biological function
- Important clinical areas of interest where proteoforms have been identified and linked to disease progression

Smith et al., *Science Advances* 7, eabk0734 (2021)

Multiple Myeloma & Light Chain Disease

- Multiple myeloma: malignancy of plasma cells characterized by a clonal expansion of abnormal B-cells
- B-cells accumulate in the bone marrow and secrete large amounts of monoclonal light chains that can deposit in organs such as kidneys leading to:
 - Light Chain Deposition Disease (LCDD) for aggregates of amorphous nature
 - AL-amyloidosis, where aggregates consist of amyloid fibrils

Amyloid light-chain (AL) amyloidosis

<https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/15718-amyloidosis>

Light Chain (LC) analysis

- Currently no possibility to predict the *in vivo* solubility and deposition behavior of a particular LC
- No link between LC abundance and disease severity
- To understand the factors affecting solubility and develop diagnostic tools, LC sequence is essential
 - RNA sequencing of B-cell clones
 - Mass Spectrometry

Sequencing of mAbs by MS

- MS extensively used for the characterization of recombinant mAbs (BUP with different enzymes)
- For unknown mAbs:
 - Combination of BUP and intact mAb mass profiling
 - Combination of BUP and middle-down proteomics on Fab (50 kDa) after sample fractionation
 - Top-down proteomics on LCs extracted from human sera for classifying plasma cell disorders (21T FT-ICR MS)

Limitation of current methods

- Gaps in sequences
- 70% sequence coverage for LC study (TDP)
- No I/L differentiation, S-S assignment

Our objective

Develop a complete *de novo* MS sequencing workflow for patient-derived LC proteoforms

Collaboration A. Büll
(Univ. Düsseldorf)

De novo sequencing: step 1 (multiple digestions)

- Enzymatic digestions

- Specific cleavage | Trypsin (K, R)
Lys C (K)
- Non-specific cleavage | Pepsin
Nepenthes fluid

- Sequence assembly

Tran N.H. et al., *Scientific Reports* 6:31730 (2016)
 Rey M et al., *Mol. Cell. Proteomics* 12 (2), 464–472 (2013)

De novo sequencing: step 2 (analysis of intact proteins)

- Sample preparation: **no digestion!**
+/- [reduction, alkylation] of S-S bonds
- LC-MS/MS on Orbitrap Fusion Lumos
Multiple fragmentation techniques
- Data analysis
Xtract (FreeStyle), ProsightLite, 5 ppm

Example for the P15 sample

Candidate seq. 1

M_{theo} : 23,461.50 Da

DLQMTQSPST LSASVGDAVT LTCRASQSLN VWLAWYQQKP GKPPKLLLYE ASNLESQVPS RFSGSGSGTE
FTLTLSSLQP DDFATYYCQQ YNSYPYTFGQ GAKLELKRTV AAPSVFLFPP SDEQLKSGTA SVVCLLNNFY
PREAKVQWKV DNALQSGNSQ ESVTEQDSKD STYSLSTLT LSKADYEKHK LYACEVTHQG LSSPVTKSFN
RGEC

Candidate seq. 2

M_{theo} : 23,462.47 Da

DLQMTQSPST LSASVGDAVT LTCRASQSLN VWLAWYQQKP GKPPKLLLYE ASDLESQVPS RFSGSGSGTE
FTLTLSSLQP DDFATYYCQQ YNSYPYTFGQ GAKLELKRTV AAPSVFLFPP SDEQLKSGTA SVVCLLNNFY
PREAKVQWKV DNALQSGNSQ ESVTEQDSKD STYSLSTLT LSKADYEKHK LYACEVTHQG LSSPVTKSFN
RGEC

P15: Intact mass analysis

$M=23,576.48$ Da

Reduction

$\Delta m = -114.93$ Da

$\Delta m = +4.03$ Da $\rightarrow$ 2 disulfide bonds

$\Delta m = -118.96$ Da $\rightarrow$ cysteinylation (119.00 Da)

$M=23,461.55$ Da

Match with sequence 1

Sequence 1
+ 2 disulfide bonds
+ 1 cysteinylation

P15: Top-down fragmentation maps

NCE
20%
25%
30%

CID

```

N D L Q|M T|Q|S|P S T L|S|A|S V|G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q S L N V|W L A|W Y Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E
51 A S|N|L|E|S|G|V|P S R F|S|G S|G|S G|T E|F T|L|T|L
76|S|S|L|Q|P D D F|A|T|Y|Y|C|Q|Q|Y|N S|Y P Y T F G Q
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S V|F|L|F|P|P S D E Q L
126 K|S G|T A S V|V|C|L|L|N N F Y P R E A K V Q W K V
151 D N A L|Q|S|G|N|S|Q|E|S|V|T|E Q|D|S K D S|T|Y|S|L
176|S|S|T|L|L|T|L|S|K|A D|Y E|K|H|K|L|L|Y A C E|V|T|H|Q|G
201|L|S|S|P V|T K|S|F N R G E C C
    
```

nr fragments: **114**
Residue cleavage: **46%**

EThcD

```

N D L Q|M T|Q|S|P S T L|S|A|S V|G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q|S L N V W L A|W Y|Q|Q|K P|G|K|P|P|K|L|L|L|Y|E
51 A S|N|L|E|S|G|V|P S R F|S|G S|G|S G|T E F T L T L
76|S|S|L|Q|P D|D|F|A|T|Y|Y|C|Q|Q|Y|N S|Y P Y T F G|Q
101|G A|K|L|L|E|L|K R T V|A|A P S|V|F L|F|P|P S|D|E|Q L
126|K|S|G|T A|S V V C|L L N|N|F|Y P|R|E|A|K|V|Q|W|K|V
151|D|N|A|L|Q|S|G|N|S|Q|E|S|V|T|E Q|D|S|K|D|S|T|Y|S L
176|S|S|T|L|L|T|L S|K|A D|Y E|K|H|K|L|L|Y A C|E V|T|H|Q|G
201|L|S|S|P V|T K|S|F N R G E|C C
    
```

nr fragments: **253**
Residue cleavage: **69%**

Reaction time + NCE
1.5 ms + 5%
5 ms + 5%
10 ms + 10%

┌ c/z fragment ions
└ b/y fragment ions
└ a/x fragment ions

NCE
10%
12%
15%

HCD

```

N D L Q|M T|Q|S|P S T L|S|A|S V|G D A V T L T C R A
26 S Q S L N V|W L A W Y|Q Q K P G K P P K L L L Y E
51 A S|N|L|E|S|G|V|P S R F|S G S|G|S G|T E F T L T L
76|S|S L|Q|P D D F|A|T|Y|Y C Q Q|Y|N S|Y P Y T F G Q
101 G A K L E L K R T V A A P S|V|F|L|F|P|P S D E Q L
126 K S G T A S V|V|C|L|L|N N F Y P R E|A K V Q W K V
151 D N A L|Q|S|G|N|S|Q|E|S|V|T|E Q|D|S K|D S|T|Y|S|L
176|S|S|T|L|L|T|L S K|A D|Y E|K|H|K|L|L|Y A C E|V|T|H|Q|G
201|L|S S|P V|T K|S|F N R G E C C
    
```

nr fragments: **99**
Residue cleavage: **44%**

UVPD

```

N D L Q M T Q|S P|S T L|S A S V|G D A V T L T C R|A
26|S Q|S L N V|W L A|W Y Q Q|K P|G|K|P|P|K|L|L|L|Y|E
51|A|S|N|L|E|S G|V|P|S R|F|S G S G S G T E|F|T L T L
76 S S L|Q|P|D|D|F|A|T Y|Y|C Q Q Y|N S|Y|P|Y T|F|G Q
101 G A K L|E L K R T V|A|A|P|S|V|F|L|F|P|P|S D E Q L
126 K S G T A S|V|V|C|L L N N F Y|P R|E|A K|V|Q W|K V
151|D|N A|L|Q|S|G N|S|Q E S|V|T E Q D S K|D|S|T|Y|S L
176|S|S T L T L|L S K|A D|Y E|K|H|K|L|L|Y A C|E V|T|H|Q|G
201|L|S S|P V|T K S|F N R G E C C
    
```

nr fragments: **164**
Residue cleavage: **54%**

Reaction time
20 ms
25 ms
30 ms

P15: Combined fragmentation man

Sequence 1

2 S-S + 1 cysteinylation

Δ mass (Exp. / Theo): 0.95 ppm

nr fragments: 375

Residue cleavage: 85%

┌ c/z fragment ions

└ b/y fragment ions

└ a/x fragment ions

5 ppm fragment mass tolerance

- Analysis of trypsin digest (+/- reduction/alkylation)
 - 100% sequence coverage
 - Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys88, Cys134 – Cys194
 - Cysteinylation on Cys214

Sarpe V, et al., *Mol. Cell. Proteomics* 15,3071-80 (2016)

P15: Ile/Leu Differentiation

z to w ion
EThcD

EThcD to generate z and w ions
 $\Delta w-z_L = -43 \text{ Da}$
 $\Delta w-z_I = -29 \text{ Da}$

Immonium ion
HCD

Small b or y ion containing I or L

↓ HCD (MS3)
 m/z 86
 ↓ HCD (MS4)
 m/z 69

P15: Ile/Leu Differentiation

↓

LLIYEASN**L**ESGVPSR

↓

LLIYEASN**L**ESGVPSR

P15 Final Sequence

κ isotype

DIQMTQSPSTLSASVGDVAVTITCRASQSLNVWLAWYQQKPGKPPKLLIYEASNLESGVP
SRFSGSGSGTEFTLTISSLQPDDFATYYCQQYNSYPYTFGGAKLEIKRTVAAPSVFIF
PPSDEQLKSGTASVVCLLNNFYPREAKVQWKVDNALQSGNSQESVTEQDSKSTYSLSS
TLLSKADYEKHKLYACEVTHQGLSSPVTKSFNRGEC*

* Cysteinylation

P8 Analysis

Intact mass analysis

Two proteoforms @:
 23,407.35 Da
 23,428.39 Da

$\Delta = +170.13$ Da Reduction
 $\Delta = +149.09$ Da Alkylation

One proteoform @:
 23,577.48 Da

A single sequence with modified Cys

De novo top-down fragmentation mass analysis

```

N D[L]Q[M]T[Q]S[P]S T[L]S[A]S[V]G[D]R V T L T C R[A] 25
26 S[Q]S L[S]S S L[A]W[Y]Q[Q]K[P]G[K]A[P]K[L]L[L]Y[D] 50
51 A[S]S L[E]T[G]V[P]S R[F]S[G]S[G]S G[T]E[F]T[L]S[L] 75
76 S[S]L[L]Q[P]D[D]F[A]T[Y]Y[C]Q H Y[N]S Y[S]L[T]F[G]Q 100
101 G T[K]V[E]L[L]K R T V[A]A[P]V[V]F[L]L[F]P[P]S[D]E[Q]L 125
126 K[S]G[T]A[S]V[V]C[L]L[L]N[N]F Y P[R]E[A]K[V]Q[W]K V 150
151 D[N]A[L]L[Q]S[G]N[S]Q[E]S[V]T[E]Q[D]S[K]D[S]T[Y]S[L] 175
176 S[S]T[L]L[T]L[S]K[A]D[Y]E[K]H[K]V[Y]A[C]E[V]T[H]Q[G] 200
201 L[L]S[S]P[V]T[K]S[F]N R G E C*
    
```

Δ mass (Exp. / Theo): -1.03 ppm
 # nr fragments: 468
 Residue cleavage: 86%

Trypsin digest

Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys88 & Cys134 – Cys194
 Cys214*: Cysteinylation or CoenzymeM (CoM)
 CoM: adjuvant in chemotherapy

P5 Analysis

Intact mass analysis

Two proteoforms @:
 23,543.49 Da
 23,776.61 Da

Reduction
 Alkylation

Two proteoforms @:
 → 23,713.62 Da
 23,946.81 Da

Two different sequences
 modified Cys

Top-down fragmentation map (5A)

```

N L[E]V[L]T[Q]S[P]G[T]L[S]L[S]P G E R[A]T L S C R[A] 25
26[S]Q[S]V[S]S S Y L[A]W[Y]Q[Q]K[P]G Q[A]P R[L]L L[Y] 50
51[D]A S T[R]A T G[L]P[D]R[F]S[G]S G S[G]A D F[L]L[L]T 75
76 L[S]S[L]E[P]E[D]F[A]M[Y] Y C Q[Q] Y G R[S] P[Y]T[F]G 100
101[P]G T[K]V[D]L[K]R T[V]A[A]P[S]V[F]L[F]P[P]S D[E]Q 125
126 L K S G T A S V[V]C[L]L N[N]F Y[P]R[E]A[K]V[Q]W[K] 150
151[V]D[N]A L Q[S]G[N]S Q[E]S[V]T[E]Q[D]S K[D]S T[Y]S 175
176[L]S[S]T[L]L T L[S]K[A]D[Y]E[K]H[K]V[Y]A[C]E[V]T[H]Q 200
201[G]L[S]S[P]V[T]K[S]F[N]R G E C* C
    
```

Δ mass (Exp. / Theo): 0.46 ppm
 Residue cleavage: 83%

Trypsin digest

Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys89 & Cys135 – Cys195
 Cys215*: Cysteinylation

P5 Analysis

Intact mass analysis

Two proteoforms @:
 23,543.49 Da
 23,776.61 Da

Reduction
 Alkylation

Two proteoforms @:
 23,713.62 Da
 → 23,946.81 Da

Two different sequences
 modified Cys

Top-down fragmentation map (5B)

Trypsin digest

Disulfides: Cys23 – Cys88 & Cys134 – Cys194
 Cys215*: Cysteinylation
 94% identity between 5A and 5B

Omnitrap platform for improved Top-Down Proteomics

- A novel segmented linear ion trap for enhanced activation and ion storage
- Arsenal of ion activation techniques: CID, ECD, EID, photo-dissociation and others...

Q-Exactive HF modified with the Omnitrap platform

- Currently available as a retrofit to the Q-Exactive/Exploris instrument series

Application areas: top-down/bottom-up proteomics, native MS, glycomics...

Q-Exactive HF modified with the Omnitrap platform

- Smooth installation (3 days), performance of the Q-Exactive HF (HeLa digest) kept the same

Application areas: top-down/bottom-up proteomics, native MS, glycomics...

P15: ECD 70 ms – MS² (nanoLC time scale)

P15: ECD (non-reduced) – MS²

Excellent sequence coverage out of the S-S bridges allowing their easy localization

P15: ECD followed by CID (non-reduced) – MS³

First S-S bond has been cleaved leading to new fragment ions

P15: ECD (reduced) – MS²

79% sequence coverage in a single experiment

Intact herceptin 150 kDa (infusion) – MS⁴

Conclusion & perspectives

- Efficient workflow for the *de novo* sequencing of light chains (clinical samples): combination of bottom-up and Top-Down Proteomics (TDP)
- TDP is essential for samples with multiple proteoforms
- The Omnitrap platform holds great promise for efficient fragmentation of intact proteins (even large ones)
More to come: VUV for S-S bond cleavage followed by CID
- Importance of data analysis, new developments required (*de novo* sequencing from top-down data)
- PI trap for proteoform separation (isoelectric focusing)

Aknowledgements

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